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(57) Abstract :

RECOMBINANT FABI ENZYME FOR DETECTION OF KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE INHIBITORS AND METHOD

THEREOF ABSTRACT The present invention discloses a method of obtaining recombinant FabI enzyme having SEQ ID 2 for the detection of Klebsiella pneumoniae inhibitors. The method includes the steps of designing a primer having SEQ ID 3 and SEQ ID 4 corresponding to fabI gene having SEQ ID 1, synthesizing a recombinant fabI gene having SEQ ID 1 and obtaining a recombinant FabI enzyme having SEQ ID 2 from fabI gene having SEQ ID 1 for detection of Klebsiella pneumoniae inhibitors. The present invention further provides a method of detection of Klebsiella pneumoniae inhibitors. The method for wherein method includes the steps of obtaining a solution comprising Klebsiella pneumoniae FabI enzyme having SEQ ID 2, crotonyl CoA, NADH and inhibitor to be detected, incubation of the solution at 20 ° to 40 ° temperature for 10 minutes to 40 minutes and examining the solution by measuring the absorbance at 340 nm for the detection of Klebsiella pneumoniae inhibitors

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